

Survey Question Catalog

for D1.1 - Landscape of PID Practices
within NFDI Services

PID4NFDI

22 December 2024

Imprint

Authored by	Jana Böhm (https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9802-113X) Sara El-Gebali (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1378-5495) Steffi Genderjahn (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8912-184X) Stephanie Hagemann-Wilholdt (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0474-2410) Torsten Kahlert (https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3264-5006) Marc Lange (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7742-3867)
Date of publication	22 December 2024
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14327774
License	This work is licensed under https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Deliverable	Part of D1.1

About

PID4NFDI (<https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>) is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through Base4NFDI.

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI. DFG Grant Number: 521466146

Contents

Introduction	1
How to Read the Questionnaire	1
Questionnaire	2
PID Service Landscape in the NFDI	2
Personal Information	3
NFDI Consortium Affiliations and PID Engagement	4
PID4NFDI Awareness, Involvement, and Support Expectations	6
Your Infrastructure(s)/Service(s) I	7
Your Infrastructure(s)/Service(s) II	12
Your Infrastructure(s)/Service(s) III	17
Current and Planned PID System Integration	22
Metadata Practices	30
Licensing and Open Science	34
Technical Interoperability: Current Efforts and Future Plans	35
Governance	38
Outreach	39
Training	41
PID Management Support	48
Your Comments and Ideas	51
Thank you for your Participation!	52
References	53

Introduction

This document contains the questionnaire of the survey entitled *PID Service Landscape in the NFDI*, which was conducted from April 9 to May 12, 2024 as part of the first phase of PID4NFDI. The survey was designed by the PID4NFDI team, implemented in LimeSurvey and completed by 34 consortia representatives with responsibilities in PID management.

The purpose of the survey was to assess the current level of PID adoption and integration among NFDI consortia and to understand their future needs. By identifying these needs and pinpointing existing gaps, the PID4NFDI team aims to develop a cross-cutting PID service that meets the evolving needs of the NFDI community.

A detailed report of the survey framework and results can be found in [1].

How to Read the Questionnaire

- Questions are numbered from 1 to 73. Some questions are divided into subparts a-c.
- Questions marked with a star (*) are mandatory. Respondents cannot proceed without answering mandatory questions.
- Filters: Some questions or response options are only shown if a specific response is given in another question. In this case, the filter is explained directly before the respective question number. Filter explanations are not shown to survey respondents.

Questionnaire

PID Service Landscape in the NFDI

Project Information

The PID4NFDI project aims to improve the use, management, and integration of Persistent Identifier (PID) services in the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). To accomplish this, the project is conducting a survey of infrastructure service providers and managers, including repositories and working environments, whether in the planning, development, or operational stages, to gather feedback on current and planned PID practices, identify existing gaps, and determine future needs.

What do we mean by PIDs?

A PID is a unique, resolvable string of characters that refers to a digital object and is permanently and unambiguously linked to it. Associated with the PID is metadata that describes the object as comprehensively as possible, at least bibliographically, and provides further information about its origin, creation, and subsequent use. PIDs improve discoverability and interoperability of the described entities, allow linking information and ease the management of metadata across services and databases.

Survey Information

The survey aims to better understand the NFDI's PID landscape, identify use cases, and analyze requirements in order to provide tailored solutions. It will be open until **May 12th, 2024**, and it takes approximately **45-60 minutes**. Participants can pause and resume the survey later. To pause the survey, navigate to the top right corner and choose 'Resume later'. Then, enter a username and a password. The survey can be continued by opening the survey URL again and providing those credentials. To get started with the survey, please accept our survey data policy stated below.

Data Usage

The PID4NFDI project team would like to emphasize that all survey responses, whether complete or incomplete, are valuable and may be used in analysis. Participation in the survey, in any capacity, provides critical data that aids in accomplishing the project's objectives. To protect respondents' identities, the findings will be released only aggregated and anonymized. Furthermore, the contact information gathered during this survey will only be used to contact

respondents who gave their consent regarding potential follow-up actions, such as additional interviews or consultation services related to the project's outcomes.

Further Information

The PID4NFDI project, funded by Base4NFDI/DFG and conducted by the team of the PID4NFDI project, aims to address the diverse requirements for PIDs across disciplines and NFDI consortia, recognising the importance of PID-related metadata for the FAIRness of research data. The project will involve core national and international players in the PID service provider and developer communities, as well as use case analysis, requirements engineering, and concept development, to lay the groundwork for future PID service development and integration within the NFDI. For further information please contact pid4nfdi@lists.nfdi.de.

There are 148 questions in this survey.

Personal Information

(Q1*) First Name:

(Q2*) Last Name:

(Q3*) E-mail address:

(Q4*) Name of your organization:

(Q5*) For our analysis of the requirements for PID services within the NFDI, we would like to conduct interviews with selected use case representatives. Would you in principle be available for an interview and may we contact you for that after the survey?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No

NFDI Consortium Affiliations and PID Engagement

The purpose of this section is to learn more about your personal role in the operation/management of infrastructures in the NFDI consortia as well as your organization's PID provider affiliation.

(Q6*) Which NFDI consortium/consortia are you representing?

Please choose all that apply:

- Base4NFDI
- BERD@NFDI
- DAPHNE4NFDI
- DataPLANT
- FAIRagro
- FAIRmat
- GHGA
- KonsortSWD
- MaRDI
- NFDI4Biodiversity
- NFDI4BIOIMAGE
- NFDI4Cat
- NFDI4Chem
- NFDI4Culture
- NFDI4DataScience
- NFDI4Earth
- NFDI4Energy
- NFDI4Health
- NFDI4Immuno
- NFDI4Ing
- NFDI-MatWerk
- NFDI4Memory
- NFDI4Microbiota
- NFDI4Objects
- NFDIxCS
- PUNCH4NFDI
- Text+

Other:

(Q7*) Are you responsible for the operation/management of an infrastructure within the NFDI consortia?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No

(Q8*) Please describe your role(s) in the NFDI consortia:

(Q9*) Is your organization a member (directly or through a consortium) of a PID provider (e.g., Crossref, DataCite, ePIC)?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Q10 is only shown if Q9 was answered "Yes":

(Q10*) Which PID provider is your organization a member of? If you are unsure about a certain PID provider, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- Crossref
- DataCite
- ePIC
- ORCID
- RAiD
- Other:

(Q11*) Are DOIs issued by your organization registered through DataCite?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Q12 is only shown if Q11 was answered "Yes":

(Q12*) How is your organisation affiliated with DataCite?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Direct Member
- Consortium Lead
- Consortium Organization (part of Consortium)
- I don't know
- Other:

PID4NFDI Awareness, Involvement, and Support Expectations

The PID4NFDI project aims to improve the use, management, and integration of PID services in the NFDI. We would like to learn what expectations you have of the project in terms of support and collaboration.

(Q13*) To what extent are you familiar with and involved in the PID4NFDI project?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Fully involved – I actively participate in the PID4NFDI project initiatives.
- Aware but not involved – I know about the PID4NFDI project but do not actively participate.
- Not aware or involved – I have no prior knowledge or involvement with the PID4NFDI project.

(Q14*) What support do you expect from PID4NFDI as a cross-consortium base service in the implementation of PIDs?

Please choose all that apply:

- Guidance on best practices for PID implementation
- Technical support and resources

- Training sessions and workshops on PID management
- Facilitation of cross-consortium collaborations
- Development of shared PID standards and policies
- I do not have any specific expectations
- I don't know
- Other:

(Q15*) What PID implementation efforts are you looking to undertake with other NFDI consortia?

Please choose all that apply:

- Collaborative development of PID standards and guidelines
- Sharing of resources and tools for PID implementation
- Joint training programs and knowledge exchange
- Coordinated efforts in advocating for PID adoption across disciplines
- Establishment of a centralized PID management framework
- I do not envisage PID implementation efforts with other consortia
- I don't know
- Other:

Your Infrastructure(s)/Service(s) I

We are interested in gaining insight into the data management services (e.g., repositories) you already offer or plan to offer within the NFDI framework. You have the option to describe up to three of your services in total. If you are representing multiple NFDI consortia throughout this survey, please describe those three services which you evaluate most important.

Please answer all questions below with respect to one specific service. You can proceed to describe a second and third service on the subsequent two pages.

(Q16a*) Would you like to add the description of a data management service that you offer or plan to offer in the NFDI?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No (we neither have nor plan any infrastructures/services related to PIDs)

Description of your first infrastructure/service:

Q17a is only shown if Q16a was answered “Yes”.

(Q17a*) Name of the infrastructure/service that requires PIDs:

Q18a is only shown if Q16a was answered “Yes”.

(Q18a*) Infrastructure/service URL:

Q19a is only shown if Q16a was answered “Yes”.

(Q19a*) Name of the organization running the infrastructure/service:

Q20a is only shown if Q16a was answered “Yes”.

(Q20a*) What is the current operational status of your infrastructure/service?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Planned
- In development
- Prototype
- Recently released
- Mature operation
- I don't know
- Other:

Q21a is only shown if Q16a was answered “Yes”.

(Q21a*) What is the main purpose of the infrastructure/service?

Please choose all that apply:

- Administrative support: Providing support for administrative tasks in a research or academic setting

- Archiving and preservation: For long-term archiving and preservation of digital or physical assets
- Collaboration and networking: Facilitating collaboration or networking among researchers or organizations
- Data analysis or processing: Providing tools or platforms for data analysis or processing
- Publication and dissemination: For publishing and distributing academic or research content
- Research data management: For managing and organizing research data
- Resource sharing publicly: Facilitating the sharing of resources such as datasets, software, or equipment
- I don't know
- Other: If the purpose does not fit into the above categories, provide a specific purpose:

Q22a is only shown if Q16a was answered "Yes". Of the answer choices below, only those are displayed which were selected in Q6 by the respondent. {Q6_other} is the text entered in the "Other" field in Q6.

(Q22a*) In which of the NFDI consortia that you are representing in this survey is the infrastructure/service (planned to be) used? If you are not sure about a specific NFDI consortium, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- Base4NFDI
- BERD@NFDI
- DAPHNE4NFDI
- DataPLANT
- FAIRagro
- FAIRmat
- GHGA
- KonsortSWD
- MaRDI
- NFDI4Biodiversity
- NFDI4BIOIMAGE
- NFDI4Cat
- NFDI4Chem
- NFDI4Culture
- NFDI4DataScience
- NFDI4Earth

- NFDI4Energy
- NFDI4Health
- NFDI4Immuno
- NFDI4Ing
- NFDI-MatWerk
- NFDI4Memory
- NFDI4Microbiota
- NFDI4Objects
- NFDIxCS
- PUNCH4NFDI
- Text+
- {Q6_other}
- None
- I don't know

Q23a is only shown if Q16a was answered "Yes".

(Q23a*) Was the infrastructure/service in existence prior to the NFDI consortium/consortia (which you checked in the previous question)?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q24a is only shown if Q16a was answered "Yes".

(Q24a*) Is the infrastructure/service used by other NFDI consortia than those you are representing in this survey?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q25a is only shown if Q16a was answered "Yes".

(Q25a*) Is the infrastructure/service used in EOSC?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q26a is only shown if Q16a was answered "Yes".

(Q26a) Please describe other uses of the infrastructure/service outside NFDI or EOSC (if there are any):

Q27a is only shown if Q16a was answered "Yes".

(Q27a*) Which software platform is deployed for the infrastructure/service? Please specify which one(s) of the software platforms is deployed in the free text field if possible and appropriate. If you are not sure about a certain type of platform, please leave the box unchecked but feel free to also add explanatory comments.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Cloud-based (platforms hosted on cloud services such as AWS, Azure, GoogleCloud, etc.):

- Open source software (DSpace, Dataverse, Fedora Commons, Invenio, etc.):

- Proprietary software (platforms developed and owned by a specific company or organization):

- Custom-built solution (unique, in-house developed software solutions):

- Research data management systems (specific software for managing research data such as REDCap, LabArchives, etc.):

- Database systems (MySQL, PostgreSQL, Oracle, etc.):

- Library management systems (systems used primarily in library settings such as Koha, Aleph, etc.):

- Other (any software platforms not listed above):

- I don't know.

Your Infrastructure(s)/Service(s) II

Q16b is only shown if Q16a was answered "Yes".

(Q16b*) Would you like to add the description of another data management service that you offer or plan to offer in the NFDI?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
 No

Description of your second infrastructure/service:

Q17b is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes".

(Q17b*) Name of the infrastructure/service that requires PIDs:

Q18b is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes".

(Q18b*) Infrastructure/service URL:

Q19b is only shown if Q16b was answered “Yes”.

(Q19b*) Name of the organization running the infrastructure/service:

Q20b is only shown if Q16b was answered “Yes”.

(Q20b*) What is the current operational status of your infrastructure/service?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Planned
- In development
- Prototype
- Recently released
- Mature operation
- I don't know
- Other:

Q21b is only shown if Q16b was answered “Yes”.

(Q21b*) What is the main purpose of the infrastructure/service?

Please choose all that apply:

- Administrative support: Providing support for administrative tasks in a research or academic setting
- Archiving and preservation: For long-term archiving and preservation of digital or physical assets
- Collaboration and networking: Facilitating collaboration or networking among researchers or organizations
- Data analysis or processing: Providing tools or platforms for data analysis or processing
- Publication and dissemination: For publishing and distributing academic or research content
- Research data management: For managing and organizing research data
- Resource sharing publicly: Facilitating the sharing of resources such as datasets, software, or equipment
- I don't know

- Other: If the purpose does not fit into the above categories, provide a specific purpose:

Q22b is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes". Of the answer choices below, only those are displayed which were selected in Q6 by the respondent. {Q6_other} is the text entered in the "Other" field in Q6.

(Q22b*) In which of the NFDI consortia that you are representing in this survey is the infrastructure/service (planned to be) used? If you are not sure about a specific NFDI consortium, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- Base4NFDI
- BERD@NFDI
- DAPHNE4NFDI
- DataPLANT
- FAIRagro
- FAIRmat
- GHGA
- KonsortSWD
- MaRDI
- NFDI4Biodiversity
- NFDI4BIOIMAGE
- NFDI4Cat
- NFDI4Chem
- NFDI4Culture
- NFDI4DataScience
- NFDI4Earth
- NFDI4Energy
- NFDI4Health
- NFDI4Immuno
- NFDI4Ing
- NFDI-MatWerk
- NFDI4Memory
- NFDI4Microbiota
- NFDI4Objects
- NFDIxCS
- PUNCH4NFDI
- Text+
- {Q6_other}

- None
- I don't know

Q23b is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes".

(Q23b*) Was the infrastructure/service in existence prior to the NFDI consortium/consortia (which you checked in the previous question)?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q24b is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes".

(Q24b*) Is the infrastructure/service used by other NFDI consortia than those you are representing in this survey?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q25b is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes".

(Q25b*) Is the infrastructure/service used in EOSC?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q26b is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes".

(Q26b) Please describe other uses of the infrastructure/service outside NFDI or EOSC (if there are any):

Q27b is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes".

(Q27b*) Which software platform is deployed for the infrastructure/service? Please specify which one(s) of the software platforms is deployed in the free text field if possible and appropriate. If you are not sure about a certain type of platform, please leave the box unchecked but feel free to also add explanatory comments.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Cloud-based (platforms hosted on cloud services such as AWS, Azure, GoogleCloud, etc.):

- Open source software (DSpace, Dataverse, Fedora Commons, Invenio, etc.):

- Proprietary software (platforms developed and owned by a specific company or organization):

- Custom-built solution (unique, in-house developed software solutions):

- Research data management systems (specific software for managing research data such as REDCap, LabArchives, etc.):

- Database systems (MySQL, PostgreSQL, Oracle, etc.):

- Library management systems (systems used primarily in library settings such as Koha, Aleph, etc.):

- Other (any software platforms not listed above):

- I don't know.

Your Infrastructure(s)/Service(s) III

Q16c is only shown if Q16b was answered "Yes".

(Q16c*) Would you like to add the description of another data management service that you offer or plan to offer in the NFDI?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
 No

Description of your third infrastructure/service:

Q17c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q17c*) Name of the infrastructure/service that requires PIDs:

Q18c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q18c*) Infrastructure/service URL:

Q19c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q19c*) Name of the organization running the infrastructure/service:

Q20c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q20c*) What is the current operational status of your infrastructure/service?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Planned
- In development
- Prototype
- Recently released
- Mature operation
- I don't know
- Other:

Q21c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q21c*) What is the main purpose of the infrastructure/service?

Please choose all that apply:

- Administrative support: Providing support for administrative tasks in a research or academic setting
- Archiving and preservation: For long-term archiving and preservation of digital or physical assets
- Collaboration and networking: Facilitating collaboration or networking among researchers or organizations
- Data analysis or processing: Providing tools or platforms for data analysis or processing
- Publication and dissemination: For publishing and distributing academic or research content
- Research data management: For managing and organizing research data
- Resource sharing publicly: Facilitating the sharing of resources such as datasets, software, or equipment
- I don't know
- Other: If the purpose does not fit into the above categories, provide a specific purpose:

Q22c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes". Of the answer choices below, only those are displayed which were selected in Q6 by the respondent. {Q6_other} is the text entered in the "Other" field in Q6.

(Q22c*) In which of the NFDI consortia that you are representing in this survey is the infrastructure/service (planned to be) used? If you are not sure about a specific NFDI consortium, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- Base4NFDI
- BERD@NFDI
- DAPHNE4NFDI
- DataPLANT
- FAIRagro
- FAIRmat
- GHGA
- KonsortSWD
- MaRDI
- NFDI4Biodiversity
- NFDI4BIOIMAGE
- NFDI4Cat
- NFDI4Chem
- NFDI4Culture
- NFDI4DataScience
- NFDI4Earth
- NFDI4Energy
- NFDI4Health
- NFDI4Immuno
- NFDI4Ing
- NFDI-MatWerk
- NFDI4Memory
- NFDI4Microbiota
- NFDI4Objects
- NFDIxCS
- PUNCH4NFDI
- Text+
- {Q6_other}
- None
- I don't know

Q23c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q23c*) Was the infrastructure/service in existence prior to the NFDI consortium/consortia (which you checked in the previous question)?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q24c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q24c*) Is the infrastructure/service used by other NFDI consortia than those you are representing in this survey?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q25c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q25c*) Is the infrastructure/service used in EOSC?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other:

Q26c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q26c) Please describe other uses of the infrastructure/service outside NFDI or EOSC (if there are any):

Q27c is only shown if Q16c was answered "Yes".

(Q27c*) Which software platform is deployed for the infrastructure/service? Please specify which one(s) of the software platforms is deployed in the free text field if possible and appropriate. If you are not sure about a certain type of platform, please leave the box unchecked but feel free to also add explanatory comments.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Cloud-based (platforms hosted on cloud services such as AWS, Azure, GoogleCloud, etc.):

- Open source software (DSpace, Dataverse, Fedora Commons, Invenio, etc.):

- Proprietary software (platforms developed and owned by a specific company or organization):

- Custom-built solution (unique, in-house developed software solutions):

- Research data management systems (specific software for managing research data such as REDCap, LabArchives, etc.):

- Database systems (MySQL, PostgreSQL, Oracle, etc.):

- Library management systems (systems used primarily in library settings such as Koha, Aleph, etc.):

- Other (any software platforms not listed above):

- I don't know.

Current and Planned PID System Integration

In this section, we are interested in both the current state and your plans regarding integration of existing identifiers in your systems.

(Q28*) Please choose all PID services your organization has worked with or plans to work with. If you are unsure about a certain PID service, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- ARK (Archival Resource Key)
- DOI - Crossref
- DOI - DataCite
- DOI - International DOI Foundation (IDF)
- ePIC (European Persistent Identifier Consortium)
- Handle System
- GRID (Global Research Identifier Database)
- GND ID (Integrated Authority File)
- ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)
- ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)
- PURL (Persistent Uniform Resource Locator)
- RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)
- ROR (Research Organization Registry)
- URNs (Uniform Resource Names)
- Wikidata ID
- Do not (plan to) work with any PID services
- I don't know
- Other:

Q29a displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q28. {Q28_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q28. For each PID service, one response option must be selected (i.e., one response option in each row).

(Q29a*) What is the current phase of PID integration for each of the services?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Current Phase of PID Integration				
	Planned	In development	Prototype	Mature	I don't know

Survey Question Catalog for D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services

ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
DOI - Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>				
DOI - DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>				
DOI - International DOI Foundation (IDF)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ePIC (European Persistent Identifier Consortium)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GRID (Global Research Identifier Database)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GND ID (Integrated Authority File)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
PURL (Persistent Uniform Resource Locator)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ROR (Research Organization Registry)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>				
{Q28_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Q29b displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q28. {Q28_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q28. For each PID service, one response option must be selected (i.e., one response option in each row).

(Q29b*) What is the approximate duration of your engagement with each PID service? If you plan to work with a PID service but have not started yet, please select 'Less than 1 year' as the anticipated duration.

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Duration of work with PID provider				
	Less than 1 year	1-2 years	2-5 years	More than 5 years	I don't know
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - International DOI Foundation (IDF)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ePIC (European Persistent Identifier Consortium)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GRID (Global Research Identifier Database)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GND ID (Integrated Authority File)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
PURL (Persistent Uniform Resource Locator)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ROR (Research Organization Registry)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

{Q28_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>				
-------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

Q30a displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q28. {Q28_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q28. For each PID service, one response option must be selected (i.e., one response option in each row).

(Q30a*) How many PIDs are already registered with each of your services?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Number of PIDs registered					
	0	1-100	101-1000	1001-10000	More than 10000	I don't know
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - International DOI Foundation (IDF)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ePIC (European Persistent Identifier Consortium)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GRID (Global Research Identifier Database)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GND ID (Integrated Authority File)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
PURL (Persistent Uniform Resource Locator)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Survey Question Catalog for D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services

RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
ROR (Research Organization Registry)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>					
{Q28_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Q30b displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q28. {Q28_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q28. For each PID service, one response option must be selected (i.e., one response option in each row).

(Q30b*) What is the estimated number of PIDs to register annually with each PID service?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Estimated PIDs to register annually					
	0	1-100	101-1000	1001-10000	More than 10000	I don't know
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DOI - International DOI Foundation (IDF)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ePIC (European Persistent Identifier Consortium)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GRID (Global Research Identifier Database)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Survey Question Catalog for D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services

GND ID (Integrated Authority File)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
PURL (Persistent Uniform Resource Locator)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
ROR (Research Organization Registry)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>					
{Q28_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Q31 displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q28. {Q28_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q28. For each PID service, one response option must be selected (i.e., one response option in each row).

(Q31*) What is your satisfaction level with respect to each PID service?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Very dissatisfied	No answer
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
DOI - Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>					
DOI - DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>					
DOI - International DOI Foundation (IDF)	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Survey Question Catalog for D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services

ePIC (European Persistent Identifier Consortium)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>					
GRID (Global Research Identifier Database)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
GND ID (Integrated Authority File)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
PURL (Persistent Uniform Resource Locator)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
ROR (Research Organization Registry)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>					
{Q28_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>					

(Q32*) What are the key factors your organization considers in deciding about PID membership? Please indicate the extent to which each of the following factors influences your decision. If you do not consider any PID membership, select 'Not applicable'.

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Strong influence	Influence	Somewhat at influence	No influence	I don't know	Not applicable
--	------------------	-----------	-----------------------	--------------	--------------	----------------

Alignment with organizational needs	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Costs factors	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Technical compatibility	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Ease of integration	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Community recommendations/ Peer influence	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Familiarity and awareness of PID and related services	<input type="checkbox"/>					

(Q33) If there are any other key factors that were not listed above, please provide them and indicate their influence:

(Q34*) For which entities do you (want to) register PIDs? Please leave the box unchecked if you are not sure about a certain type of resource.

Please choose all that apply:

- Datasets
- DMPs (Data Management Plans)
- Grants
- Instruments
- Metadata
- Models
- Multimedia files (images, videos, etc.)
- Ontologies, terminologies
- Organizations
- Peer reviews

- Physical objects (artefacts, specimens, etc.)
- Preprints
- Research publications
- Research projects
- Software, code, and tools
- Standards
- Study registrations
- Tables, charts
- Theses and dissertations
- Variables in datasets
- Workflows
- I don't know
- Don't (want to) register PIDs
- Other:

Metadata Practices

The aim of this section is to understand your current usage of metadata with respect to metadata standards, linkage, and quality.

(Q35*) Which metadata schemas are currently used in your repository/repositories for PID registration? If you are not sure about a certain schema, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- Dublin Core Simple or Qualified
- MARC (Machine-Readable Cataloguing)
- MODS (Metadata Object Description Schema)
- DataCite Metadata Schema
- Schema.org
- DCAT
- I don't know
- Not applicable
- Other:

(Q36) Describe any extensions or mappings to metadata schemas your team/organization has developed, detailing their purpose and how to access them. This may involve customizations for specific requirements, disciplines, projects, or data varieties. Share insights on these adjustments and their uses.

(Q37*) What methods do you use to establish and record links between different (types of) PIDs? This might include how you connect various research outputs, such as datasets, publications, and researchers, using PIDs. If you are not sure whether a certain method is used, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- Metadata fields (within datasets, articles, etc.)
- DataCite's metadata schema-connection metadata (e.g., relatedIdentifier, nameIdentifier)
- Dedicated linking tools (specific software or platforms)
- Reference management systems
- Manual recording (e.g., spreadsheets, documents)
- Programmatic methods (e.g., scripts, automated processes)
- Integration with repository or archival systems
- I don't know
- Not applicable
- Other:

(Q38*) Are you involved in any groups or forums, either within or external to your organization, that focus on metadata issues, including discussions on standards, quality, and enhancements?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No

Q39 is only shown if Q38 was answered "Yes".

(Q39*) Are the discussions in the metadata groups focused on specific scientific fields or disciplines (genomics, microscopy and imaging, physical samples, etc.)?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Q40 is only shown if Q38 was answered "Yes".

(Q40) Please provide a brief description of the metadata groups, highlighting their main activities, focus areas, and if applicable, the specific fields or disciplines they address:

(Q41*) Does your organization offer training sessions, workshops, or resources to educate staff or users about the importance of complete and accurate metadata for PIDs?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes, for staff and users
- Only for staff
- Only for users
- No
- I don't know

For each resource type, one response option must be selected (i.e., one response option in each row).

(Q42*) Please select the option that best describes the change in registration trends with PIDs in your organization over the past 5 years. If a particular type of resource is not managed by your organization, please select 'Not applicable'. For any trends not listed that you may have observed, please describe them in the subsequent textbox.

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Signifi	Moder	Slightl	Remai	Decre	I don't	Not
--	---------	-------	---------	-------	-------	---------	-----

	cantly increa sed	ately increa sed	y increa sed	ned the same	ased	know	applic able
Datasets	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Software and tools	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Research text publications	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Data management plans	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Multimedia files (images, videos, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Physical objects (artefacts, specimens, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Connection metadata, e.g., to people and organizations	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Research projects	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Theses and dissertations	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Training material	<input type="checkbox"/>						

(Q43) Other trends that you may have observed:

(Q44*) To identify common practices and potential areas for standardisation or improvement of metadata management, we would like to understand the utilization patterns of different metadata fields in the resource types (such as

datasets, publications, or other digital objects) you deal with in your repositories and services.

For the resource types managed by your organization, can you provide data on the most and least frequently used fields and may we contact you about this after the survey?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No

Licensing and Open Science

The purpose of this section is to learn about your institution's policies regarding licensing and Open Science.

(Q45*) What types of licenses are applied in your organization's repositories and services? This question aims to identify the range of licensing types your organization uses for digital content, data, or software within your repositories and services, to gain an understanding on how content is shared and reused in your organization's digital ecosystem. If you are not sure whether a certain license is applied, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- CC BY (Creative Commons Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)
- GPL (GNU General Public License)
- MIT License
- Apache License
- CC0 (Public Domain Dedication)
- No specific license applied
- I don't know
- Not applicable
- Other:

(Q46*) Does your institution have a policy or guidelines regarding the use of licenses for research outputs such as data, publications, and software?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Not applicable

(Q47*) Does your institution have a formal policy or guidelines for the implementation and use of PIDs for research outputs?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Not applicable

(Q48*) Does your institution have a formal policy or set of guidelines to promote and support Open Science?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Not applicable

Technical Interoperability: Current Efforts and Future Plans

We would like to learn more about your efforts, plans or wishes regarding technical interoperability.

(Q49*) Which of the following standards and protocols does your repository implement to ensure interoperability with various PID systems and services? If you are not sure whether a certain standard or protocol is used, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting)

- RESTful APIs (Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface)
- SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol)
- Linked Data and RDF (Resource Description Framework)
- I don't know
- Not applicable
- Other:

(Q50*) Does your repository utilize APIs for interacting with PID services, such as creating, updating, or retrieving PID data?

Please choose all that apply:

- Yes, we use DataCite's APIs
- No, we do not use APIs for PID service integration
- I don't know
- Yes, we use APIs from other PID providers. Please specify any additional PID providers you work with:

Q51 is only displayed if “Yes, we use DataCite's APIs” was selected in Q50.

(Q51*) Which of the following DataCite APIs does your organization currently utilize? If you are not sure about a certain API, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- DataCite REST API
- DataCite MDS API
- DataCite GraphQL API
- DataCite OAI-PMH
- I don't know

Q52 is only displayed if “Yes, we use DataCite's APIs” was selected in Q50.

(Q52*) Please select the features of the DataCite API that your organization uses most frequently.

Please choose all that apply:

- DOI registration and metadata creation/update
- Metadata retrieval/harvesting

- Reporting and analytics for own use
- Integration with external systems (e.g., electronic lab notebooks)
- I don't know
- Other:

(Q53*) Does your infrastructure/service have any plans or projects aimed at enhancing technical interoperability in the near future?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Not applicable

Q54 is only shown if Q53 was answered "Yes".

(Q54) Briefly describe the major interoperability goals for the next year:

(Q55) Which improvements or changes would you like to see in the area of technical interoperability from PID providers?

Governance

In this section we would like to learn more about the governance model of your organization and your specific role in it.

(Q56*) What is your involvement in the decision-making process regarding the implementation and management of PIDs within your organization?

Please choose all that apply:

- Strategic decision-maker: Directly responsible for making final decisions on PID implementation strategies and policies.
- Advisory role: Provide recommendations or expert advice influencing PID strategy and policy decisions.
- Technical implementation and support: Involved in the technical aspects of PID system integration, support, and maintenance.
- Policy and standards development: Participate in developing and setting policies and standards related to PID usage and management.
- Operational management: Oversee the day-to-day operations and management of PID systems.
- Data management and curation: Involved in managing and curating data that uses PIDs, ensuring best practices in metadata and data linkage.
- Research and development: Engaged in researching new PID technologies or methodologies for organizational adoption.
- No direct involvement: Not directly involved in PID decision-making or implementation processes.
- Other:

(Q57*) Does your organization have a formal governance structure or committee dedicated to the management and oversight of PID policies and practices?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Not applicable

(Q58*) What are the primary challenges your organization encounters in the governance of PID implementation and management?

Please choose all that apply:

- Insufficient staff resources: Struggling with limited personnel dedicated to PID management tasks.
- Absence of dedicated budget: Lack of a designated budget for the sustained management of PIDs.

- Project-based budgeting: Reliance on project-specific funding for PID management, without a strategy for long-term sustainability.
- Diverse PID provider requirements: Difficulties in navigating and complying with the governance models and business requirements of different PID providers.
- License-related restrictions: Limitations imposed by licensing agreements affecting PID usage or management.
- NFDI governance complexities: Issues arising from the distributed responsibility and consortium-based governance structure of the NFDI affecting PID strategies.
- Integration with existing systems: Challenges in integrating PIDs smoothly with current information systems and workflows.
- Ensuring PID persistence and resolution: Ensuring that PIDs remain resolvable overtime, maintaining link integrity.
- Adapting to evolving standards and practices: Keeping up with changes in PID standards, technologies, and best practices.
- I don't know
- Not applicable
- Other:

Outreach

In this section we ask about your organization's practices to reach out to your target groups.

(Q59*) Does your organization undertake outreach activities to promote PID awareness or educate about PIDs?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Q60 is only shown if Q59 was answered "Yes".

(Q60*) Please indicate the primary audiences targeted in your organization's PID outreach activities.

Please choose all that apply:

- Administrators
- General public
- IT professionals
- Data curators, librarians
- Policy makers
- Researchers
- I don't know
- Other:

Q61 is only shown if Q59 was answered "Yes".

(Q61*) Which tools and platforms does your organization use for outreach activities about PIDs? If you are not sure about a certain tool or platform, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- In-person workshops
- Online webinars/workshops
- Hybrid (online and in-person) webinars/workshops
- In-person conferences and events
- Online conferences and events
- Hybrid (online and in-person) conferences and events
- Email newsletters
- Blogs/Websites
- Collaborations with other organizations
- Print media
- Social media
- I don't know
- Other:

Q62 is only displayed if "Social media" was selected in Q61.

(Q62) Which social media do you use for outreach activities about PIDs?

Q63 is only shown if Q59 was answered "Yes".

(Q63*) How can PID providers better support your organization's training and outreach efforts?

Please choose all that apply:

- Providing customized training materials
- Providing training material in local language
- Offering specialized webinars or workshops
- Collaborating on joint outreach initiatives
- Offering guidance on best practices for PID usage
- Facilitating networking opportunities with other organizations
- Providing access to educational resources
- Providing onboardings
- Providing low-threshold information material for end users (researchers) on added-values of PIDs
- I don't know
- Not applicable
- Other:

Training

We would like to learn more about frequency, format, and topics of training you or members of your team attended on the registration or use of PIDs.

(Q64*) In the past two years, did you or members of your team attend any training courses offered by one of the listed PID services on the registration or use of PIDs? If you are not sure about a certain PID service, please leave the corresponding box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- ARK (Archival Resource Key)
- Crossref
- DataCite
- ePIC
- Handle System
- GND ID
- ORCID
- PURL
- RAiD

- ROR
- URNs (Uniform Resource Names)
- Wikidata ID
- Did not attend any training courses
- Other:

Q65a displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q64. One response option must be selected for each PID service (i.e., one response option in each row). {Q64_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q64.

(Q65a*) Indicate how often you participate in training events and webinars.

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Frequency			
	Frequently (more than 6 times a year)	Occasionally (2-3 times a year)	Rarely (once a year or less)	I don't know
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ePIC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GND ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ORCID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
PURL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
RAiD	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ROR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

{Q64_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
-------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

Q65b displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q64. One response option must be selected for each PID service (i.e., one response option in each row). {Q64_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q64.

(Q65b*) Indicate if you actively use informational materials provided by the PID service for the implementation and use of PIDs.

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Active use of information materials		
	Yes	No	I don't know
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ePIC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GND ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ORCID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
PURL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
RAiD	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ROR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
{Q64_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q66 displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q64. Multiple response options can be selected for each PID service (i.e., multiple in each row). {Q64_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q64.

(Q66*) For each PID service, indicate which format was the training you attended. Please choose the appropriate responses for each item:

	Attended Training Formats					
	Webinars	Instructional videos	Support documentation	Training Sessions	I don't know	Other
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
ePIC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
GND ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
ORCID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
PURL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
RAiD	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
ROR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>

Survey Question Catalog for D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services

Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>				
{Q64_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>				

Q67 displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q64. Multiple response options can be selected for each PID service (i.e., multiple in each row). {Q64_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q64.

(Q67*) For each PID service, indicate which PID topics have been covered by training sessions you have attended.

Please choose the appropriate responses for each item:

	Attended Training Topics								
	PID fundamentals	PIDs for specific research entities	System-specific implementation of PIDs	Reuse potential of PIDs	Metadata and metadata standards	APIs	Data citation	I don't know	Other:
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
ePIC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
GND ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>

Survey Question Catalog for D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services

ORCID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
PURL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
RAiD	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
ROR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
{Q64_oth er}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								

Q68 displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q64. Multiple response options can be selected for each PID service (i.e., multiple in each row). {Q64_other} is the text entered in the "Other" field in Q64.

(Q68*) For each PID service, indicate for which PID topics you would like training courses or information material to be made available.

Please choose the appropriate responses for each item:

	Requested Training Topics								
	PID fundamentals	PIDs for specific research entities	System-specific implementation of PIDs	Reuse potential of PIDs	Metadata and metadata standards	APIs	Data citation	I don't know	Other:
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>

Survey Question Catalog for D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services

Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
ePIC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
GND ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
ORCID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
PURL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
RAiD	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
ROR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								
{Q64_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>								

(Q69*) Who delivers the training on metadata completeness for PIDs within your organization?

Please choose one of the following answers:

- Provided by our organization's internal resources
- Commissioned to specialized external organizations
- A combination of internal and external resources
- No such training is provided
- I don't know
- Other:

PID Management Support

In this section we ask about external support services which you reached out to in order to receive support with the implementation or management of PIDs.

(Q70*) Please specify if your organization has sought external support for managing or implementing PIDs, including technical help, consulting, training, or resources from experts or DataCite/ORCID consortium leads (e.g., TIBconsortium). Select all services for which your organization has sought support. If you are not sure whether your organization has sought support for a certain service, please leave the box unchecked.

Please choose all that apply:

- ARK (Archival Resource Key)
- Crossref
- DataCite
- ePIC
- Handle System
- GND ID
- ORCID
- PURL
- RAiD
- ROR
- URNs (Uniform Resource Names)
- Wikidata ID
- Did not reach for any support
- Other:

Q71 displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q70. One response option must be selected for each PID service (i.e., one in each row). {Q70_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q70.

(Q71*) Indicate how often you reach to support from outside your organization for the implementation or management of PIDs.

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Frequency		
	Regularly (at least once a month)	Occasionally (as needed)	I don't know
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ePIC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
GND ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ORCID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
PURL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
RAiD	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ROR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
{Q70_other}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q72 displays all PID services selected by the respondent in Q70. Multiple response options can be selected for each PID service (i.e., multiple in each row). {Q70_other} is the text entered in the “Other” field in Q70.

(Q72*) For each PID service, please select the types of support services you frequently require. If you are not sure whether a certain type of support service is frequently required, please leave the box unchecked.

Survey Question Catalog for D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices within NFDI Services

Please choose the appropriate responses for each item:

	Required Support Services							
	Technical assistance (e.g., API issues, integration challenges)	Billing and membership queries	Guidance on best practices (e.g., metadata standards, PID management)	Training-related support	Platform navigation and usage	Community engagement (e.g., forums, peer support)	I don't know	Other:
ARK (Archival Resource Key)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
Crossref	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
DataCite	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
ePIC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
Handle System	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
GND ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
ORCID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
PURL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
RAiD	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>
ROR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>

URNs (Uniform Resource Names)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>						
Wikidata ID	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>						
{Q70_oth er}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="text"/>						

Your Comments and Ideas

Thank you, you are almost done!

On this page, you have the option to leave any comments you would like us to know. This could be, for example, personal ideas, challenges or needs with respect to any of the previous topics or other features related to PIDs that could be of interest for the project. Also, if you might have a use case that you want to share with us, you can indicate it here and leave a short description.

Please make sure that you submit the survey by clicking on the 'Submit' button at the bottom of the page such that your comments will be saved.

(Q73) Anything you would like us to know?

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.

Thank you for your participation!

If you have questions about the survey or would like to learn more about the survey results, please write to pid4nfdi@lists.nfdi.de. For further information on the project, please visit <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>.

References

- [1] El-Gebali, S., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Böhm, J., & Kahlert, T. (2024). D1.1 Landscape of PID practices within NFDI services. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277479>.